

The holy Niels of Århus (older text)

By Svend Clausen, TBC

Entry tags: Miracle tales, Christianity, Christian, Catholic, Religious Group, Latin Text, Text, Hagiography, Medieval Christianity, Catholic text

The text discusses the holy Niels of Århus, a Danish prince who died in 1180. He was of royal blood as the son of king Knud III of Denmark, who had been murdered by the henchmen of a rival king during a civil war in 1157. Niels appears in a few contemporary documents, but apart from that not much is known about his life except for what is told in the two preserved texts about him. He is remembered as a local Danish saint who was venerated in Århus diocese in Jutland during the middle ages. Two hagiographic texts are known about him: an older one and a younger one. Even though these two have been preserved together as part of a collective manuscript, it is necessary to distinguish between them as they are quite different not only in dating and in their individual background of creation, but also stylistically. Compared to the younger one, the older saint's legend about the holy Niels of Århus follows the classic form of hagiography, structurally, much more than the younger one does. Originally the older text contained an introduction first, although now only the opening words are preserved of this. The bulk of the text describes his life and death followed by the description of almost a sort of episcopal translation of his body: although apparently not reflecting any such actual episcopal translation, this part of the text slightly imitates a translation story when it tells the miracle story about how his grave site was selected and approved by the bishop. The text then ends with a selection of miracle stories connected to his cult. Two papal letters demanding both the miraculous events and his saintliness to be examined are added at the end. As for dating the text, the two papal letters at the end are dated for 1254 and 1255, respectively. A miracle story speaks of abbot Vilhelm of Æbelholt monastery in Denmark in a way suggesting that this must have happened after the papal canonization of Vilhelm took place in 1224. The last group of miracle stories are also clearly dated between 1250 and 1252. Except for these miracle stories, though, there are few indications obviously dating his saint's vita, although it does seem clear that it could not have been written until only several decades after his death. Therefore, the text as a whole has usually been dated for c. 1254-1255 as it was probably written to coincide with the application to the pope for the canonization of Niels. It is this application now reflected in the two preserved papal letters. The holy Niels was venerated in Århus diocese continuously throughout the middle ages, although he was never formally canonized by the church. His cult does, however, seem to have had a strong following amongst the people locally.

Date Range: 1254 CE - 1255 CE

Region: Århus diocese, Denmark, medieval period

Region tags: Denmark

Map very roughly showing the borders of Århus diocese in Denmark during the 13th C. when the text about the holy Niels was written here.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: M.CL. GERTZ: Vitae Sanctorum Danorum, København, 1908-1912

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://wiki.app.uib.no/medieval/index.php?title=Sanctus_Nicolaus_Arhusiensis

– Source 1 Description: background information on the source in English

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: not available

Notes: But Gertz's book can be found online

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Church

– Yes

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Specify: Although not known with certainty where it was kept, in the medieval period an edition of the text must have been kept with the holy chapter in Århus diocese: probably in the diocesan library/archive or in the cathedral where it may have been used as basis for liturgical celebrations used liturgically

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: It is preserved in copy on paper nowadays, but it was probably written on parchment originally

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: preparation (making) of the parchment

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: the original manuscript is not preserved

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

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Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– No

Notes: The answer is probably both yes and no at the same time. The author were not necessarily paid for writing this text, but the author was probably a cathedral canon in Århus diocese and as such paid by the institution who had financial interests in this saint's cult.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– No

Notes: Once again the answer is probably yes and no at the same time as the text produced by the institution who also controlled the religious infrastructure of the cult and its texts.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– No

Notes: Once again yes and no at the same time in the sense that the cathedral canons can be viewed as political officials.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

Notes: Yes in the sense that the holy Niels was venerated officially within the diocese.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

Notes: The text was probably written by religious specialists in the form of a cathedral canon in Århus diocese.

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: male

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Yes

Notes: most likely Danish

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– Yes

Notes: Not necessarily always, but in many cases probably yes.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: The text must have been considered his official saint's vita, although his cult was only venerated officially within Århus diocese where it may have been used as basis for liturgical celebrations as basis of liturgical celebrations. This can be the case even though his cult was not necessarily part of the official liturgy within the diocese and even though there are no preserved traces of liturgy. However, in the case of the extremely local cult of the priest holy Anders within Roskilde diocese (see entry on Aaders), there are preserved traces of liturgy even though holy Anders never became a part of the official liturgy of Roskilde diocese. This appears to make it likely that some sort of liturgy could have existed also in the case of holy Niels.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– No

Notes: Not necessarily, but new miracles stories could e.g. happen/appear and be added as is reflected in the younger text about the holy Niels.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– Yes

Notes: But probably depends on the definition

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– No

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Yes

Notes: male

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: yes in the sense that the younger Niels vita reflects this.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– No

Notes: The younger Niels vita could have been so in the medieval period, but the holy Niels has not been venerated in Denmark since the Reformation.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: written in latin

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: the text may have been used as basis for liturgical celebrations

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
 - Yes
- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ How often do the rituals take place?
 - Specify: probably annual veneration on a specific date
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
 - No
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
 - No
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices?
 - No
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?
 - No
- ↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
 - No

Is there material significance to the text?

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– No

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– No

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– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: none of the above

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The original manuscript is not preserved.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is both an older and a younger saint's text about the holy Niels. There is no proof that the younger vita was viewed as less proper, although only the older vita was used in the application for canonization. This is not necessarily because the younger was viewed as less proper, though, but because no new application was made.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The older saint's vita about the holy Niels is preserved in a collection of texts about the holy Niels. The collection also contains the younger saint's vita about him and copies of two papal letters as well as all the older and younger miracle stories etc.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: The older saint's vita was probably written in order for it to be used together with an application for official canonization sent to the Pope in Rome. Thus making the cult official was probably a main point in the writing of it.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: the younger saint's vita reflect that it can be added to.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - No
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No

- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that hagiography can be described in this way.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: hagiography

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: although yes in the sense that Niels was probably venerated annually on the basis of the text.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: The miraculous events relating to how the gravesite of Niels in a wooden chapel by the sea was chosen is described.

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

–Specify: Niels' own actions when preparing for his own death and the events and miracles before his burial etc.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Notes: in the churches and in the wooden chapel

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: none of the above

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The original manuscript is not preserved.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

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Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

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Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

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– Yes

Notes: The miraculous events relating to how the gravesite of Niels in a wooden chapel by the sea was chosen is described.

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Niels' s own actions when preparing for his own death and the events and miracles before his burial etc.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Notes: in the churches and in the wooden chapel

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: none of the above

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

- No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Most likely it was written by a canon who was member of the holy chapter of Århus diocese.

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Hardly controlled it in the sense that they didn't want the text to spread, but in the sense that it probably did not spread much beyond Århus diocese.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: none of the above

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Most likely it was written by a canon who was member of the holy chapter of Århus diocese.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Hardly controlled it in the sense that they didn't want the text to spread, but in the sense that it probably did not spread much beyond Århus diocese.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: none of the above

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

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Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

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Education

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Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

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